

Assessment of Knowledge towards Fair Trade Practice of Workers of Apparel Industry in Jaipur Industry

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Abstract:- The present study aims in assessing the knowledge & awareness towards fair trade practices of workers of apparel industry in Jaipur industry. Importance of sustainable fair practices was brought to notice of the apparel industry workers for their welfare. It gave an idea of how industries in India are running. Eighty apparel industry workers from two different units of different age groups, different educational qualifications & from different working sector in the units were approached to collect the data through self structured interview schedule in Jaipur city.

The data was analyzed through Descriptive - frequency & percentage method to find out the effect of demographic factors on knowledge of workers of apparel industries.

The results of the study revealed that 60% of the respondents were totally unaware about the application of fair-trade production, 1.75% of the workers were aware about sustainable fair-trade practices & 21.25% of them were confused about the term & were very less interested. It was also found that respondents didn't had much knowledge about wage rates, working hours, child laboring & sustainable steps towards apparel industry.

On assessing the knowledge of workers an interview session was conducted while data collection to spread awareness about fair trade , its policies& sustainability.

Keywords:- Fashion, Sustainability, Fair trade, Workers, Consumers, Awareness, Knowledge, Apparel, Textile.

I. INTRODUCTION

Assessment of knowledge towards fair trade practice of workers of apparel industry in Jaipur industry.

A. Apparel Industry

Apparel industry or garment industry refers to the types of trading method and industry along with the production and value addition in the clothing and garment industry, which starts with textile industry, embellishment like embroidery, prints till the final product, moving from fashion industries to apparel retailers for trading along with second hand & recycled textile clothes.

Textile Industry is providing one of the most basic needs of people and the holds importance; maintaining sustained growth for improving quality of life.

The Indian textile industry is one of the largest in the world with a massive raw material and textiles manufacturing base. Our economy is largely dependent on the textile manufacturing and trade in addition to other major industries. About 27% of the foreign exchange earnings are on account of export of textiles and clothing alone. The textiles and clothing sector contributes about 14% to the industrial production and 3% to the gross domestic product of the country.

India's textile industry is one of the economy's largest. In 2000/01, the textile and garment industries accounted for about 4 percent of GDP, 14 percent of industrial output, 18 percent of industrial employment, and 27 percent of export earnings.

B. Consequences of Textile Production Process

Textile industry is one of the most effectively harmful industry in the world & is one of the major reason in causing environment pollution. Production of textiles or apparel includes a long process, which includes a large amount of harmful chemical usage, water wastage, fabric left outs. The manufacturing & construction process of textile, their use, maintenance and disposal have a direct effect upon environmental degradation & wastage of raw materials and natural objects. Due to the large amount of apparel products being manufactured, used and disposed every day leaves a direct impact on environment in every step of product life cycle. Textile manufacturing processes has an impact on environment i.e. use of high amount of water while growing natural fibers, energy in all finishing processes and consumption of chemicals substances for dyeing and printing.

C. Fair Trade

Fair trade in fashion industry is a social and economic movement which promotes international standards of ethical trading policies, labor and environmental policies in the trading of goods or commodities. It includes principles such as payment at a fair price and gender equality.

Where fair trade is a way of doing business, ethical production refers to the production of a textile product and encompasses the whole life cycle of the product from the raw materials, through the finishing processes, to the construction.

II. FINDING & FUTURE SCOPE

Through a research process, it was found that the researches on Fair trade policies & sustainability in context of apparel industry workers were accessed in terms of acceptability of the fair trade. The concept of fair trade products from the perspective of consumer was also explored by many researchers to access their attitude, awareness & knowledge of apparel industry workers towards sustainability & fair trade policies. But the main purpose of these studies was to know the acceptability of fair trade in Indian market and its apparel units & the output of which was that only a research was found that too was not much relevant towards the study. Hence, there was a need to explore, knowledge & awareness of apparel industry workers towards fair trade policies under sustainability.

To investigate the relation between knowledge & awareness of fair trade policies & workers or consumers perception, it was essential to analyze the researches done on this topics and find the research gap. This chapter provides a deeper understanding of workers knowledge on sustainability & fair trade in Indian apparel industries, its hazards, impact of awareness programme on acceptability of fair trade policies.

III. METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out in following steps: Knowledge and awareness on sustainability. Knowledge and awareness on fair trade.

- Apparel industry and its impact on environment.
- awareness of fair trade to apparel industry workers.
- Knowledge of fair trade consumers

In the process to achieving the objectives of the study, it is very important to follow an organized precise approach / process to present and interpret the results of the study. This process deals with the research part adopted for the present investigation. The present investigation aims to study the knowledge & awareness of workers towards fair trade practices in apparel industry in Jaipur city. The study was carried out using interview method. Assessing knowledge and creating awareness about fair trade policies, wages and sustainability was the main objective of the study.

IV. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Review of literature aims to bring in front the relevant available studies ,data & Facts limited and specific to the research topic. Main aim of this chapter was to access the information related to the subject of research which would further help in finding the result, with help of already available facts & studies done on similar topics. Basic and fundamental information was collected about consumer, worker & producer's knowledge and perception towards fair trade policies & sustainability, impact of awareness program in workers knowledge & understanding, on apparel industry towards wastage consumption and sustainable development of textile & apparels.

Enough literature was not available on fair trade in context to Indian market & following industries which is current demand due to the sustainability factors and growth of worker class.

Strähle, Wirtz & Köksal (2016) explained fashion buying behaviour Of consumertowards sustainability labels. This study was based on fair trade practice in fashion industries of Germany. The tool for study collection was a structural questioner which was implemented on 128 consumers in Germany. The major finding of the study revealed that maximum number of respondents were unaware about the term fair trade products and selected practice exist is fashion industry. The study also revealed that either fashion industries should remove this practice from their product categories.

Doran, Josephine (2009) studied and experimented on ethical sustainable fair trade practices. The sample of the study was 262 consumers who have strong behavioural intention to avoid the purchase of sweatshop clothing. The samples were selected through purposive sampling technique. The major findings of the study shows that 68% of respondents had either not purchased sweatshop free clothing, which has been properly studied and verified and has also been implemented in many fields but when we talk about fashion industries these are identified but not implemented by the workers and also by the work providers. It has been a topic in Research and Development part but not of the actual practices been followed by the clothing sector. The media and researchers have worked on highlighting the sweatshop labour concerns in fashion industries to be the one of the major issue which is effecting the consumer behaviour or their decision to buy the products and services. The study reveals the fact that the avoidable behaviour of the buyers has impact on consumers or end users to check the fair trade in sustainability before buying the product and services.

Meghan, B.S(2013) studied and acknowledged the behaviour, attitude & knowledge of consumers towards fair trade products. The study examined that fairtrade is current issue for developing countries retailers and consumers perception are now a days concern about social responsibility, But researcher also identified that in spite of knowledge among consumers and retailers it has not been taken much in use . The study also identified that sale of limited available fair trade products have increased in US through different retail chains. However, the sector of fair trade consumers has not been identified.

Sarah(2015) studied the effect of fair trade policies on agricultural industry labours in America. She related fair trade within regional steps of sustainable change in environment. She promoted certification process, founded the local available policies promoting fair trade. She collected data from 3 sources that is from her own study from local production houses, from studies available about labour contracts with fair trade value chains. The study identified that there are few policies available that provide advantages to waged agricultural labours. She also identified few norms & regulations against the industries who are

working with inadequate fair trade policies and taught the workers about their rights.

Rosella & Katherine(2019) studies that sustainability plays an important role in fashion/apparel industry looking forward at current state of environmental health. However, after a survey done with ethical fair trade consumers the point identified was that finding and identifying real fair trade product and unethical product is way too difficult. They stood for a point that Corporate social responsibility(CSR) communications, which also includes Code of ethics COE should arrange for a way through which consumers can learn properly about the brand or companies identity & value. They highlighted the importance of finding differences between ethical & unethical business in context to saving the consumers from getting cheated , protecting worker rights and to threaten the unethical companies to work properly.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The importance of assessing knowledge of apparel industry workers towards fair trade is the first step to address the environment issues related to sustainable fair trade in fashion industries. Keeping this thing in mind a survey method was adopted & conducted among apparel industry workers of Jaipur city through a questionnaire which was made to fulfill the requirements of the study. The questionnaire was made in a method which could access the knowledge & perception of workers of apparel industries.

A. Demographic profile of the respondents:

Section 1: Knowledge of respondents towards fair trade.

To assess the knowledge of apparel industry workers towards fair trade an interview schedule was used. Questions on fair trade like wages, working hours, sustainability, fabric consumption & other factors related to same were included in the questionnaire. Questions where of agree/ disagree & undecided type responses. Responses of all questions have represented in form of frequency & percentage.

N=80

LEVEL OF EDUCATION	f	%
Illiterate	46	57.5
5 th pass	28	35
8 th pass	06	7.5

Table 1: Distribution of the respondents on the basis of level of education

Table; 1 reveals that 57.5% of the workers were illiterate, 35% were 5th pass & only 7.5% of them were 8th pass, which states that maximum no. of the respondents

were illiterate and less- literate due to which they were occupied in these industries and had little or no knowledge about the fair trade policies and ongoing market rates.

N=80

LEVEL OF AWARENESS	f	%
Agree	09	11.25
Disagree	41	51.25
Undecided	30	37.5

Table 2: Distribution of the respondents on basis of awareness about wages in apparel industry

Table; 2 reveals that maximum number 51.25% were unaware about wages in apparel industry, only 11.25% of the workers were aware & 37.5% of them were confused about the term, which states that maximum no. of the respondents

didn't had any knowledge about the term. They were not informed about the wage criteria given by the government which is in their benefit.

N=80

LEVEL OF AWARENESS	f	%
Agree	32	40
Disagree	11	13.75
Undecided	37	46.25

Table 3: Distribution of respondents on the basis of awareness about the minimum production expenses

Table; 3 reveals that 40% of the workers were aware about minimum production expenses to be paid in apparel units for production, 13.75% were totally unaware & 46.25%

of them were confused about the term as they heard about this but didn't knew the exact meaning.

N=80		
LEVEL OF AWARENESS	f	%
Agree	22	27.5
Disagree	06	7.5
Undecided	52	65

Table 4: Distribution of respondent on basis of awareness about child labour in apparel industry

Table; 4 reveals that 27.5% of the workers were aware about child labour, 7.5% were totally unaware & 65% of them

were confused about the term as they do not know the laws & regulations of the industry towards child labour.

N=80		
LEVEL OF AGREEMENT	f	%
Agree	01	1.25
Disagree	05	6.25
Undecided	74	92.5

Table 5: Distribution of respondent on basis of agreement towards quality identification of sustainable goods

Table; 5 reveals that 92.5% of them were confused quality identification of sustainable goods. 1.25% of the workers were aware about it & 6.25% were totally unaware about the term. This indicates that maximum no. of the

respondents were not aware about sustainable goods identification as they haven't listened or worked upon any of such products till date.

N=80		
LEVEL OF AGREEMENT	f	%
Agree	24	30
Disagree	08	10
Undecided	48	60

Table 6: Distribution of respondent on the basis of awareness about the fair- trade raw materials

Table; 6 reveals that 30% of the workers were aware about fair-trade raw material to be used for sustainable production, 10% were totally unaware due to level of

knowledge & 60% of them were confused about the term as they were not informed about the term and also they were not working in a fair trade unit.

N=80		
LEVEL OF AGREEMENT	f	%
Agree	29	36.25
Disagree	38	47.5
Undecided	13	16.25

Table 7: Distribution of respondent on the basis of awareness about sustainable fair trade policies

Table; 7 reveals that 36.25% of the workers were aware about sustainable fair-trade policies existing in apparel industry, 47.5% were totally unaware due to level of

knowledge & 16.25% of them were confused about the term due to illiteracy, less awareness & knowledge & interest towards the same.

N=80		
LEVEL OF AGREEMENT	f	%
Agree	13	16.25
Disagree	17	21.25
Undecided	50	62.5

Table 8: Distribution of respondent on the basis of awareness about agricultural products

Table; 8 reveals that 16.25% of the workers were agreeing that agricultural products are sustainable products, 21.25% were totally unaware about this & 62.5% of them were confused about the term. As they aware provided info

regarding sustainability they connected the terms but still maximum no. of the respondents were confused about the term.

N=80		
LEVEL OF AWARENESS	f	%
Agree	16	20
Disagree	27	33.75
Undecided	37	46.25

Table 9: Distribution of respondent on the basis of awareness about working hour policy

Table; 9 reveals that 20% of the workers were aware about working hour policy existed in apparel units, 33.75% were totally unaware about this & maximum 46.25% of

them were confused about the term as they have no idea about fair trade production & policies exists in apparel industry.

N=80		
LEVEL OF AGREEMENT	f	%
Agree	13	16.25
Disagree	20	25
Undecided	47	58.75

Table 10: Distribution of respondent on the basis of agreement about the fair trade logo

Table; 10 reveals that 16.25% of the workers were aware about fair-trade logo as they have seen somewhere in their work, 25% were totally unaware as they have never

seen this earlier & only 5.75% respondents of them were confused about the term as they had never seen it before.

N=80		
LEVEL OF AWARENESS	f	%
Agree	38	47.5
Disagree	12	15
Undecided	30	37.5

Table 11: Distribution of respondent on the basis of awareness about the fair trade producers

Table; 11 reveals that 47.5% of the workers were aware about minimum production expenses, 15% were totally unaware & 37.5% of them were confused about the term as

the workers have never worked with fair trade producers. Also, there is no fair trade apparel unit in Jaipur.

N=80		
LEVEL OF AGREEMENT	f	%
Agree	6	7.5
Disagree	13	16.25
Undecided	61	76.25

Table 12: Distribution of respondent on the basis of awareness about the standard wages

Table; 12 reveals that 7.5% of the workers were aware about standard wages, 16.25% were totally unaware & 76.25% of them were confused about the term as they never

worked upon standard wages. As there are many workers who are ready to work in less wages.

N=80		
LEVEL OF AWARENESS	f	%
Agree	15	18.75
Disagree	48	60
Undecided	17	21.25

Table 13: Distribution of respondent on the basis of awareness about the sustainable fair-trade practices

Table; 13 reveals that 1.75% of the workers were aware about sustainable fair-trade practices, 60% were totally unaware & 21.25% of them were confused about the term as

the units they worked in didn't worked upon sustainable fair trade practices.

N=80

LEVEL OF AWARENESS	f	%
Agree	15	18.75
Disagree	48	60
Undecided	17	21.25

Table 14: Distribution of respondent on the basis of awareness about consumption & disposal of garment

Table; 14 reveals that 33.75% of the workers were aware about consumption & disposal of garment, 37.5% were totally unaware & 28.75% of them were confused

about the term which states the workers don't take much interest in knowing the use and after use of garments.

N=80

cut-outs.

LEVEL OF AWARENESS	f	%
Agree	13	16.25
Disagree	41	51.25
Undecided	46	32.5

Table 15: Distribution of respondent on the basis of awareness about reuse of waste

Table; 15 reveals that 16.25% of the workers were aware about reuse of waste cut-outs , 51.25% were totally unaware & 32.5% of them were confused about the term as in apparel units waste cut-outs are thrown away.

fair trade & are able to understand the significance of sustainable production of textile & clothing.

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VI. CONCLUSION

The word fair trade is mostly recognized and trusted as sustainable label in the world. Fair trade is a arrangement made to help out the producers & suppliers in developing countries achieve sustainable, fair & equitable trade relationships. The implementation of fair trade in Indian market fully depends on customers or consumers who are willing to make active ethical choices in available products and competitions in the market that has direct impact on upliftment of the society and providing workers proper facilities and actual rates.

Textile is a major part of the basic need of human being and consumers are usually not aware about the manufacturing of different types of textiles and hazards involved therein. The changing or fast fashion of the apparel & fashion industry has forced consumers to buy more clothing. This has resulted in more consumption of less pricing clothing and due to this consumers buy more and dispose more.

The present study focuses on spreading awareness towards fair trade policies among apparel industry consumers was an attempt to assess the knowledge and perception of workers & consumers of Jaipur city to change their attitude towards sustainable fashion and make their behaviour friendly to accept fair trade policies & products. When consumers lack knowledge about fair trade & sustainability this affect their behaviour and perception.

Hence the study was planned to find the knowledge of apparel industry workers towards fair trade & sustainable apparel production. The study further spreads awareness among them so that they have a positive attitude towards